

Citation bias in the CONSORT 2010 comments on blinding

Harri Hemilä¹

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Comment on:

Moher D, Hopewell S, Schulz KF, Montori V, Gøtzsche PC, Devereaux PJ, Elbourne D, Egger M, Altman DG.

CONSORT 2010 explanation and elaboration: updated guidelines for reporting parallel group randomised trials.

BMJ 2010;340:c869.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20332511>

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In their discussion on the CONSORT guidelines for clinical trial reporting, Moher et al. state that accurate and transparent reporting are important (1). About blinding, they write as follows: “*Participants may respond differently if they are aware of their treatment assignment ... These biases have been well documented*” (6 citations).

One of the six cited papers is the trial by Karlowski et al. (2) which reported that the benefit of vitamin C against the common cold was explained by the break in the blind. In the abstract: [the vitamin C] “*effects demonstrated might be explained equally well by a break in the double blind*” (2). The Karlowski trial has frequently been cited by clinical trialists as an example of the importance of blinding, and by specialists in nutrition and infectious diseases as an evidence that vitamin C does not have a real effect on the common cold (3,4).

Given that Moher et al. argue for the importance of good quality reporting of controlled trials, it is surprising that they ignore obvious shortcomings in the Karlowski paper. The trial report is inconsistent with several of the CONSORT 2010 items (1).

1 Harri Hemilä, MD, PhD

Department of Public Health, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, FINLAND.

<https://www.mv.helsinki.fi/home/hemila>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4710-307X>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/?term=hemila+h>

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

<https://researchportal.helsinki.fi/en/persons/harri-hemil%C3%A4>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

Item 1b. Abstract : *“The abstract should accurately reflect what is included in the full journal article”* [in their text] and *“for the primary outcome, a result for each group and the estimated effect size and its precision”* [in Table 2]. Karlowski et al.'s abstract does not describe the results for the primary outcome. Their results section describes: *“Volunteers taking placebo had colds of a mean duration of 7.14 days, while those taking 3 gm of ascorbic acid (groups 2 and 3) had colds of a mean duration of 6.59 days and those taking 6 gm had colds of a mean duration of 5.92 days. Thus, each 3-gm increment of ascorbic acid would appear to shorten the mean duration of a cold by approximately half a day”*, but this is not mentioned in their abstract (2). Instead, in their abstract Karlowski et al. describe the findings of a post hoc subgroup analysis based on guessing the treatment, even though half of recorded common cold episodes were missing from the subgroup analysis without any explanation.

Item 3b. *“Important changes to methods after trial commencement (such as eligibility criteria), with reasons”* (1). Although Karlowski et al. did motivate their post hoc subgroup analysis, they did not give any details about the groups who were “blinded” and “unblinded” after the trial. Karlowski administered vitamin C in two ways using 2x2 factorial design: prophylactically each day over the study and therapeutically for 5 days when a participant caught a cold. Thus, a participant can be “unblinded” for either or both of the supplementation methods. However, Karlowski et al. did not report which supplementation method the “unblinded” participants guessed correctly.

Item 12b. *“Methods for additional analyses, such as subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses. ... Because of the high risk for spurious findings, subgroup analyses are often discouraged. Post hoc subgroup comparisons (analyses done after looking at the data) are especially likely not to be confirmed by further studies. Such analyses do not have great credibility”* (1). In the Karlowski trial, the subgroup analysis by “guessing the treatment” was a post hoc subgroup comparison. The methods of the subgroup analysis are poorly described, see Items 3b and 13b. Furthermore, Karlowski et al. used “correct answer” as a surrogate for “knowing” without considering that many answers were correct purely by guesswork. Thus, the main finding of the Karlowski study, on the basis of their abstract - the reason for Moher et al. to cite the study (1) - is based on a poorly described post hoc subgroup analysis.

Item 13b. *“For each group, losses and exclusions after randomisation, together with reasons”* (1). In the Karlowski trial, 42% (105/249) of recorded common cold episodes were missing from the subgroup analysis (4), but no reasons are given to this exclusion. Furthermore, the maximum effect of vitamin C on common cold duration was even greater in the

“missing group” than in the entire study population (4), but this was not commented on by Karlowski et al.

Item 20. “*Trial limitations, addressing sources of potential bias, imprecision, and, if relevant, multiplicity of analyses*” (1). In the abstract, the main finding of the Karlowski trial was the subgroup difference in the effect of vitamin C by guessing the treatment. However, the shortcomings of the subgroup analysis are not properly discussed. There are numerous logical inconsistencies that should have been noted by the original authors (3-5).

The Karlowski trial is particularly important for two reasons: for methodological and for biological reasons. First, it has been and still is used as an example of the “placebo effect in action” (1,3). Second, the Karlowski trial is a frequent citation in medical textbooks when stating that vitamin C is ineffective against the common cold (3), whereas placebo-controlled trials have shown quite consistently that it is effective, even though the practical significance is unsettled (8).

Over a decade ago, I pointed out the problems of the Karlowski subgroup analysis (4). The principal investigator of the Karlowski trial did not find errors in my reanalysis (6,7). The study cannot be considered as an example of placebo effect in action.

Thus, while Moher et al. propose the CONSORT items as a guide for authors who write trial reports and for the readers of such reports, they ignore those items when they refer to the Karlowski trial as an evidence justifying their claim that “*biases [caused by the awareness of their treatment assignment] have been well documented*” (1).

Furthermore, Moher et al. do not refer to a recent large meta-analysis of 202 trials with 60 clinical conditions, which directly compared a placebo arm with a no-treatment arm (9). Most of the included trials had three arms so that the third arm received an active intervention. Therefore, the participants of the placebo arms did not know whether they were given the active treatment or not (blinded to the treatment), whereas the no-treatment participants knew that they were not being treated. Thus, this meta-analysis measures the importance of blinding. Placebo had no effect when the outcome was binary or objective, whereas it had effects on several subjective and continuous outcomes (9). Furthermore, this meta-analysis gives estimates for bias potentially caused by the lack of blinding in trials on various clinical conditions. It would seem much more useful to consider the specific conditions when the lack of blinding may cause substantial bias, in contrast to universal statements such as “*biases have been well documented*”(1).

Citation bias means that authors refer to studies that are consistent with their preconceptions (10). There is evident citation bias in the article by Moher et al. (1). When arguing that the lack of blinding causes bias in controlled trials, they refer to an old study which supports their

preconceptions (2), ignoring the evidence which indicates that the old study was erroneously analyzed (3-5). In addition, they ignore an extensive meta-analysis which analyses the effect of blinding on 60 clinical conditions (9). Although trial reports should describe the level of blinding, bias caused by the awareness of treatment assignment has not been “well documented”.

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